

Cause of Death Mortality Modelling using Constrained Penalised Splines and Forecast Reconciliation Approach

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KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Sub-Saharan Africa has seen sharp increases in life expectancy over the past few decades, one of the regions experiencing the fastest mortality improvements. Although vast literature on mortality modelling and forecasting exists, most of them relates to developed countries, with sparse literature focusing on this region. Kenya's life expectancy, for example, has been increasing at a rate of 0.88 per year over the last two decades. Here, we propose a cause-of-death (CoD) mortality modelling technique that, to the best of our knowledge, has not been applied to CoD mortality modelling before. Compared to aggregate mortality, CoD mortality data contains detailed information on mortality trends, which enables us to understand the critical drivers of mortality and incorporate cause-specific opinions on mortality patterns. CoD data for males and females from 1990 to 2017 are utilised, and the top 10 causes of death are used for modelling. We apply the novel constrained penalised splines (CPS) model to individual causes and aggregate mortality. Forecast reconciliation forecasting approaches are applied to ensure coherence. We show that incorporating prior knowledge of mortality patterns significantly improves forecast accuracy, especially for mortalities with irregular patterns. Additionally, we compare the results from the CPS model with those from an extension of the Lee-Carter (LC) model and the mainstream penalised splines (PS) model. We show that the constraint parameters can be appropriately chosen to produce similar results as those from LC and PS models. Finally, we apply the CPS model to calculate two lifespan measures: mean life span and life span variations and apply residual bootstrap to project these measures. These results show an increase in projected average life expectancy by 3.3 years to 73.3 when compared with the United Nations (UN) estimates and have implications when modelling future healthcare system costs.

1. Introduction

Mortality investigation has been the centerpiece of most actuarial research in recent decades. Given unprecedented improvements in mortality experiences, actuaries and demographers have put substantial effort into modelling and forecasting mortality with acceptable precision. Measuring and forecasting mortality trends apply to life insurance pricing and healthcare financing¹ (Tuljapurkar et al., 2000), government budgeting and planning (Thomas, 2018), among other fields.

As people continue to live longer, the uncertainty on the implication of an ageing population increases, and so does the mortality forecasting uncertainty (Horiuchi & Wilmoth, 1997). This is further exacerbated by irregular mortality patterns and improvements over time (Tuljapurkar & Boe, 1998).

Several models have been applied to mortality modelling and forecasting, which exploits trends underlying observed mortality improvements (e.g. see Booth & Tickle, 2008; Cairns et al., 2008, 2009; Dowd et al., 2010, among others for a detailed review). These models have subsequently been applied to cause of death (CoD) mortality in an attempt to identify the key drivers of mortality improvements observed in all-cause mortality (see Li et al., 2019, and the references therein).

Although these models have been successful in ex-

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¹Especially at old ages.

30 ploiting recent advances in CoD modelling by forecast reconciliation approaches (see Hyndman et al., 2011; Wickramasuriya et al., 2018, for methodology review) to ensure coherence in the forecasts, sometimes they still produce implausible forecasts due to the rigid modelling structure imposed.

35 Additionally, when projecting cause-specific mortality, incorporating expert opinion, such as anticipated medical breakthroughs, would significantly improve the accuracy of the forecasts. Methods that combine well-established smoothing models, as well as the incorporation of prior demographic information, have recently been proposed (see Camarda, 2019, for a comprehensive methodology review). It has been shown that when these methodologies are applied to all-cause mortality, it results in better forecasts with plausible age profiles and time trends (Camarda, 2019). Therefore, this paper's motivation is to investigate whether applying this new invention to cause-specific mortality, together with the forecast reconciliation approach, would lead to an overall improvement in mortality forecasts.

50 There has been increased research attention to CoD mortality modelling because of its potential to provide more insight into the drivers of mortality patterns. However, modelling mortality by cause increases the noise in the model, (Li et al., 2019). A compromise on the amount of noise introduced by this low-level series into the modelling process and the amount of information harnessed by modelling by cause has to be reached. For this paper, we have classified CoD mortality modelling methodologies into five main categories.

First are those that estimate mortality indices by fitting stochastic models, such as the Lee-Carter (LC) model (R. D. Lee & Carter, 1992) to individual CoD. They then apply time series processes, commonly random walk processes with a drift, to predict the mortality index (e.g. see Alai et al., 2018). While these approaches have widely been applied in practice, they cannot guarantee that the CoD forecasts will add up to the aggregate mortality forecasts, even if they are simultaneously modelled. Additionally, causes with the highest mortality would drive mortality forecasts, and the incorporation of expert opinion is not intuitive.

75 More recently, methodologies that utilise CoD dependency structure by modelling marginal mortalities have been proposed (Li & Lu, 2018). While these methods provide more insight into the by-cause mortality structures, their non-intuitive modelling has limited their practical applications. Additionally, they do not guarantee consistent aggregation of mortality forecasts.

80 Canudas-Romo et al. (2016) have explored models in which mortality forecasts are produced such that it achieves expert clinical and public health opinion on future improvements. While these methods would be desirable for CoD, they are subjective, resource intensive², and expert opinions may defer.

85 Fourthly, are models such as those explored by Fore-

90 man et al. (2018) which assess the association between mortality and such clinical indicators as smoking status, physical activity and body mass index; and apply stochastic models to these clinical factors. While attractive for the level of detail, they are resource intensive³, relies on medical data, which may either not be readily available or have many confidentiality caveats. Such model development and documentation may be complex, impeding the interpretability of the results.

95 Lastly are forecast reconciliation approaches as explored by Li et al., 2019. This approach utilises the hierarchical structure of CoD mortality by fitting appropriate stochastic mortality models to aggregate and by-cause mortalities and forecasting them. The forecasts are then reconciled using an appropriate technique to ensure coherence. Since mortality forms a natural hierarchy, interpreting and communicating results from this method are easier and more intuitive. Although it addresses the drawback of non-coherent forecasts inherent in all the other four methods, incorporating expert opinion is not as intuitive.

100 This paper, therefore, makes a five-fold literal and pragmatic contribution. Firstly, we show that constraining future CoD mortality patterns to be within a range of plausible age profiles and time trends using previously observed patterns significantly improves the accuracy of the forecasts. We also show that incorporating prior knowledge of mortality patterns significantly improves forecast accuracy, especially for mortalities with irregular patterns. Secondly, although Camarda (2019) applied this method, the Constrained Penalised Splines (CPS) model, to Danish females and US males, we apply this novel CPS model to individual causes, as well as aggregate mortality. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to apply this methodology to CoD mortality data. Additionally, we have fitted the models using Kenyan mortality data. Various forecast reconciliation approaches have been evaluated to ensure coherence in the forecasts. Again, to our knowledge, this is the first time COD mortality modelling has been applied to Kenyan data. Additionally, most recent mortality research is based on developed countries with limited literature on developing countries. Given such global policies and goals as the achievement of UHC goal (World Health Organisation [WHO], 2019), as well as sharp increases in life expectancy in developing countries (The World Bank [WB], 2020), the need for accurate models that relate to developing countries' circumstances can never be overemphasised. More importantly, infant mortalities are considerably higher in these countries as compared to developed countries (see figure (1)), and therefore mortality models should consider this. We, therefore, detach infant mortality from the rest of the years by using a modified age domain basis, separating infant mortality development from the rest of the years, leading to more accurate infant mortality modelling. This is a common practice when developing life tables, (Chiang, 1984). Finally, we apply the CPS model to cal-

³Especially since they heavily rely on opinions from a wide range of experts.

²Especially if there are many CoDs.

150 culate two lifespan measures. We show that applying CPS models leads to an increase in projected average life expectancy by 3.3 years to 73.3 compared with the United Nations (UN) estimates, which have various implications, including healthcare costs.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows. First, the notations used in the rest of this paper are outlined in section (2), followed by a description of the sources of data utilised in the study in section (3). Section (4) entails a description and preliminary analysis of the CoD data. The methods applied in this paper are outlined in section (5), followed by their empirical applications in section (6). The paper concludes with a discussion and conclusions in section (7).

2. Notations

Here, we define notations that will be used throughout the paper.

$D^c(x, t)$: Number of period deaths (henceforth just deaths) by cause c during the year t of individuals aged x last birthday.

$E(x, t)$: An estimate of the total life years in year t of individuals aged x last birthday. They are independent of any cause of death.

165 $m^c(x, t)$: Observed central death rate for cause c during year t of individuals aged x last birthday, estimated as $m^c(x, t) = D^c(x, t)/E(x, t)$.

$m(x, t)$: Overall observed central death rate in year t for individuals aged x last birthday, defined as $m(x, t) = \sum_{\forall c} m^c(x, t)$.

$\mu(x, t)$: Fitted central death rates, also referred to as the force of mortality here.

3. Data Description

170 The data used in this study were obtained from the Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network (GBD, 2017), which provides a global health data catalogue created and maintained by the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME) - an independent global health research centre based in the University of Washington. Data from IHME are not only replicable but also reliable because the methods used in their estimation are rigorously peer-reviewed and are in line with modern statistical methods. It also complies with the guidelines for accurate and transparent health estimates reporting (GATHER) (Stevens et al., 2016; WHO, 2014), a best practice for reporting health estimates. All the methodologies used to collate the data are transparent and readily accessible. This, therefore, means that upon the emergence of new information, these can easily be incorporated into the existing estimates. Additionally, uncertainty intervals are provided, making it easy to check the reliability of both methods and the data.

185 Most mortality studies use data from the Human Mortality Database (HMD, 2021). In this study, this was

Figure 1: Combined infant mortality per a thousand live births in Kenya and five other countries; Australia, Nigeria, South Africa (SA), United Kingdom (UK) and the United States of America (USA) from 1960 to 2019. Data Source: (The World Bank, 2021).

not possible as Kenya was not part of the countries with their mortalities uploaded to the HMD database. Therefore, we intend to make the data estimated in this study available for future research. For our study, we have utilised all the available historical mortality data for Kenya from 1990 to 2017. The analyses were done for males and females separately. Only the results for female mortality are presented in this paper. Male mortality analysis follow-on and the results are available upon request.

4. Cause-of-Death Data

In this study, CoD data for males and females were obtained and used to fit the models. This paper presents results from models fitted using female mortality. Since CoD data have an aggregation structure, we can exploit modern hierarchical time series modelling techniques to model by-cause mortality. Wilmoth (1995) have suggested that such methods can improve mortality forecasts. Data on the complete list of CoD were obtained, containing 293 granular causes of death. At this level of granularity, it is essential to limit the causes being modelled to minimise the impact of noise typically evident at these levels, (Wickramasuriya et al., 2018).

The Kenya National Bureau of Statistics [KNBS]'s officially published top ten causes of death by the number of registered deaths in Kenya were used. These were malaria, pneumonia, cancer, HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis (TB), anaemia, road traffic accidents⁴, other accidents, heart disease and meningitis (KNBS, 2018). Based on the data obtained, reclassifications were essential to align to the ICD⁵⁻¹⁰ reporting. The following reclassifications were used for modelling (see table (3) for the respective ICD codes): malaria, Lower Respiratory Infections (LRI), cancer, HIV/AIDS, TB, nutritional deficiencies (deficiency for short), transport accidents (injuries for short), cardiovascular diseases (cardiovas-

⁴This included deaths that occurred after the road accidents have been reported.

⁵International Classification of Diseases.

⁶The 10th edition of ICD.

cular for short), meningitis and others⁷.

We utilised all available data for Kenya, spanning 28 years, from 1990 to 2017. Two data sets were obtained: by-cause data for the complete list of causes of death in Kenya and population data. The by-cause deaths data were available for early, late and post-neonatal; age ranges 1-4 and five-year intervals after that, and a final open interval 95+. Single-year age-specific death counts were then estimated using the method described by Wilmoth et al. (see Wilmoth et al., 2017, appendix J.) for ages 0, 1 and 2; then applied Hyman's monotone cubic spline (Hyman, 1983), achieved by applying derivative constraints to the interpolant by extending de Boor-Swartz monotonicity limit.

Although the aggregation of data in age groups reduces the noise in death data, it has been established by Gelman and Auerbach (2016) that these aggregations introduce biases to mortality tables, emanating from the evolution of the age structure of the inner population within any particular age interval. The population data were obtained yearly and age-specific. Lexis diagrams were then used to estimate period deaths and exposures using the method described by Wilmoth et al. (2017), which were then used to estimate the mortality rates, $m^c(x, t)$. Due to the period data estimation methods, 2017 mortality is not obtainable.

Figure (2) shows the age structure of female mortality in Kenya between 1990 and 2017. For modelling purposes, the data were cut-off at age 85. Beyond this age, most of the data would be unreliable. The yearly data are estimated using such records as surveys and censuses, and it is known that the figures reported, especially at old ages, are often overstated (see Andreev, 2004).

Figure 2: Age pattern of female all-cause mortality for Kenya between 1990 and 2016.

Kenyan female mortality depicts the general expected mortality structure: high infant mortality, the accident hump and the exponential increase in mortality after that. While mortality has generally improved over the years and for all ages, it has consistently improved for infant and childbearing ages. Two things to note: infant mortality is still significantly higher, and maternal mortality has significantly improved over the last seven years. This coincides with the roll-out of Linda Mama health insurance⁸, a free maternity health insurance

programme funded by the Kenyan government. This can be evidence that the services are fruitful, and increased funding should be encouraged.

Figure (3) shows that historically, observed mortality has generally declined over time, with the highest mortality improvements occurring at younger ages. Infant mortality has consistently improved, with under-five mortalities experiencing the most significant improvements post 2000 (see figure 3a) with an almost linear downward trend. However, mortality seems to have worsened between ages 6 and 9 over the years (e.g. see figure (3b)). However, a general linear improvement is seen again at pre-teenage⁹ in all years (e.g. see figure (3c)) after which it becomes erratic at mid adolescence¹⁰ (see figure (3d)).

Although there is a general improvement after age 17, this has not been consistent. Notably, mortality worsens in the first seven years and an almost linear improvement afterwards (e.g. see figures (3e - 3h)). This mortality shape over the sexually active years coincides with the HIV/AIDS epidemic. The point at which mortality starts to decline linearly seems to be shifting towards 2003 as age advances (figures (3e - 3g)), which also coincides with the commencement of subsidised ARV¹¹ provision by the Kenyan government. This is also the childbearing age. After the childbearing age, mortality regains its almost linear decline over all years (e.g. see figures (3h & 3i)), until older age where mortality improvements have been noticeably lower, and erratic due to unreliable data. Other than mid-adolescence, mortality improvement rates seem to be approximately linear over the years.

Figure (4) shows rainbow plots of different causes of death. Segregating the mortality into its constituents helps us understand the mortality trends and the source of variations across the age and time domain. For example, removing the effects of HIV/AIDS (figure (4j)) almost eliminates the hump seen in figure (2) between ages 20 and 40. It can also be observed that not all causes have consistently experienced mortality improvements over the years. For example, TB mortalities have been high, with Cancer and Cardiovascular showing slight improvement over the years.

Although HIV/AIDS and malaria have experienced the most significant improvements over the years, the decline has not been consistent. On the age domain, mortality improvements or worsening has not been consistent across the age spectrum for all causes. For instance, while the improvements from meningitis and injuries seem consistent across all ages, cancer seems to have had mixed changes: significant mortality improvements between ages 50 and 65, worsening at old age and almost no change between ages 20 and 40. This is enough evidence that we not only need to model these granular causes but also need a flexible model to capture these variations in age. The model should also be able to cut-off specific trends that are not expected in the future without throwing away an entire dataset.

national hospital insurance fund (NHIF)'s [website](#).

⁹Between ages 10 and 12, also early adolescence.

¹⁰Ages 13 to 16.

¹¹Antiretroviral drugs.

Figure 3: evolution of historical age-specific female mortality for selected ages between 1990 and 2016.

330 For example, it is unlikely that the peculiar pre-2000 mortality shape for HIV/AIDS between ages 5 and 15 would be observed again.

5. Methods

5.1. Cause of Death and Competing Risks

335 It is impractical to estimate by-cause mortality in a competing risk setting empirically. In the real world, all causes exist. It is difficult to eliminate other causes; therefore, the ultimate cause of death is always one with the minimum lifetime of all the causes. This effectively means that for n causes, $n - 1$ lifetimes are right-censored. More formally, consider two causes, α and β , with net lifetimes¹² τ_α and τ_β . The ultimate lifetime, assuming only these two causes, shall be

$$\tau = \min(\tau_\alpha, \tau_\beta) \quad (1)$$

and the lifetime distribution function is given by

$$P(\tau > x) = P(\tau_\alpha > x, \tau_\beta > x) \quad (2)$$

$$= \exp\left(-\int_0^x \mu(y) dy\right) \quad (3)$$

345 However, due to right-censoring, equation (2) is not readily estimable. Mathematically, the by-cause mortality

$$P(\tau_i < x + \delta | \tau = \tau_i, \tau \geq x)$$

for cause i between ages $(x, x + \delta]$ and for a small δ is not directly estimable. Assuming independence of

¹²Lifetimes if only that cause existed, and not any other.

by-cause lifetimes means equations (2) and (3) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} P(\tau > x) &= P(\tau_\alpha > x) \times P(\tau_\beta > x) \\ &= \exp\left(-\int_0^x \mu_\alpha(y) dy\right) \times \exp\left(-\int_0^x \mu_\beta(y) dy\right) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, by-cause mortality can directly be estimated from the by-cause death rates, $D^c(x, t)$ (see Boumezoued et al., 2018; Dimitrova et al., 2013, and references therein for detailed discussions).

5.2. Constrained Penalised Splines (CPS) Model

When using the P-splines, it is assumed that data on the number of deaths observed at each age and year are available alongside their exposures. In a matrix notation, this can be represented as:

$$\mathbf{Y} = \begin{pmatrix} y_{11} & y_{12} & \cdots & y_{1n} \\ y_{21} & y_{22} & \cdots & y_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ y_{m1} & y_{m2} & \cdots & y_{mn} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{E} = \begin{pmatrix} e_{11} & e_{12} & \cdots & e_{1n} \\ e_{21} & e_{22} & \cdots & e_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ e_{m1} & e_{m2} & \cdots & e_{mn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

360 where \mathbf{Y} and \mathbf{E} are matrices of deaths and exposures observed for m ages, $1, 2, \dots, m$, and n years, $1, 2, \dots, n$, respectively. It is also assumed that deaths

Figure 4: Rainbow plots for individual causes of death between 1990 and 2016.

occur following a Poisson distribution such that:

$$y_{ij} \sim Po(\mu_{ij}e_{ij}) \quad \text{where} \quad \mu_{ij} = \frac{y_{ij}}{e_{ij}} \quad (6)$$

The objective is to obtain a smoothed estimate of μ_{ij} , $\hat{\mu}_{ij}$. The expected number of deaths, using logarithm as the link function, can be expressed as:

$$\log(\mathbb{E}[y]) = \log(\mathbf{e}) + \log(\mu) = \log(\mathbf{e}) + \eta \quad (7)$$

Where $\log(\mathbf{e})$ is the offset and η a linear predictor such that, in the usual GLM context:

$$\eta = \mathbf{X}\alpha \quad (8)$$

Defining \mathbf{B} as a banded matrix of k B-splines, $\{B_1(x), B_2(x), \dots, B_k(x)\}$, the linear predictor can be rewritten as:

$$\eta = \mathbf{B}\alpha \quad (9)$$

Suppose the estimated regression matrices of B-splines for the marginal models are \mathbf{B}_y ¹³ for the columns and \mathbf{B}_a ¹⁴ for the rows, then the two-dimensional regression matrix is given by the Kronecker product:

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B}_y \otimes \mathbf{B}_a \quad (10)$$

With $y \times a$ regression coefficients, α , which can be used to build a forecasting model by applying a penalised log-likelihood approach. To incorporate prior mortality knowledge, constraints on the time and age domains are imposed.

On the age domain, the constraint is obtained by calculating the relative derivative:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \hat{\mu} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \log(\hat{\mu}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \hat{\eta} \quad (11)$$

$$= \left(\mathbf{B}_{n_1} \otimes \frac{1}{h} [q^{-1} \mathbf{B}_a^\vee - q^{-1} \mathbf{B}_a^{\vee-1}] \right) \hat{\alpha} \quad (12)$$

Where n_1 are the observed years, h the distance of the knots, \vee the position of the B-splines in \mathbf{B}_a , and q the degree of the spline polynomials. On the time domain, similar arguments are made leading up to:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{n}_1} \hat{\mu} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{n}_1} \log(\hat{\mu}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{n}_1} \hat{\eta} = \mathbf{D}_{n_1}^{n_1} \hat{\alpha} \quad (13)$$

computed over \mathbf{B}_y . This way, it is possible to constrain future mortality to lie within a certain interval of the observed rate of ageing δ , the choice of which is conveniently highly dependent on the forecaster's professional judgement based on past mortality trends. These opinions can be incorporated into forecasting by constructing appropriate confidence limits (see Camarda, 2019, and references therein for a more detailed discussion).

Finally, infant mortality is detached from the rest of the years by using the modified basis

$$\mathbf{B}_a = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \mathbf{0}_{1 \times k_a} \\ \mathbf{0}_{(m-1) \times 1} & \mathbf{B}_a^* \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{B}_a^* does not include age zero and hence an $(m-1) \times k_a$ matrix. The first entry of \mathbf{D}_a is replaced with a zero to indicate the non-inclusion of infant mortality.

¹³That is over years $1, 2, \dots, n$.

¹⁴That is over ages $1, 2, \dots, m$.

5.3. Hierarchical Modelling

Mortality forms a natural hierarchy since the individual COD mortality would add to the total mortality for a given gender. The following forecast reconciliation approaches have been applied to ensure that the structure of the forecasted hierarchical time series is maintained.

5.3.1. Top-down Reconciliation

Here, the assumption is that the top series contains sufficient¹⁵ information, and therefore the forecasts obtained from this series can be considered to be more accurate. We forecast the top and bottom series, then adjust the lower hierarchy series to ensure the hierarchical structure is maintained. This is done by estimating the proportion

$$p_j = \prod_{l=0}^{K-1} \frac{\hat{y}_{j,h}^{(l)}}{\hat{S}_{j,h}^{(l+1)}}$$

for $j = 1, \dots, m_K$, which is used to disaggregate the h -step ahead forecasts of the top level of a hierarchical series with K levels. $\hat{y}_{j,h}^{(l)}$ and $\hat{S}_{j,h}^{(l+1)}$ represents the h -ahead base forecasts, and the sum of the base forecasts correspond to a node, which is l levels above node j .

5.3.2. Bottom-up Reconciliation

Here, the models were fitted to individual bottom series, and then the forecasts were summed up to obtain the aggregate series above it. The summation was repeated for each hierarchy. Using the notations already defined, the forecasts can be expressed as

$$\hat{y}_h = \mathbf{S} \hat{y}_{k,h}$$

Where \mathbf{S} is a summing matrix.

5.3.3. Trace Minimization Reconciliation

The h -step ahead forecasts can be represented as:

$$\hat{y}_h = \mathbf{S} \beta_h + \varepsilon_h$$

Where \mathbf{S} is the structure of the hierarchical series and $\varepsilon_h \sim N(0, \Sigma_h)$. Assuming that the forecasts conform to the hierarchical structure, then:

$$\varepsilon_h \approx \mathbf{S} \varepsilon_{K,h}$$

And so it can be shown (Hyndman et al., 2011) that:

$$\hat{\beta}_h = \left(\mathbf{S}' \Sigma_h^\dagger \mathbf{S} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{S}' \Sigma_h^\dagger \hat{y}_n(h)$$

Is the best unbiased estimator of $\hat{\beta}_h$, producing the reconciled forecasts:

$$\hat{y}_h = \mathbf{S} \left(\mathbf{S}' \Sigma_h^\dagger \mathbf{S} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{S}' \Sigma_h^\dagger \hat{y}_n(h)$$

Σ_h^\dagger is neither known nor identifiable. When $\Sigma_h^\dagger = \mathbb{I}$, it reduces to an ordinary least squares (OLS) estimator

¹⁵And somewhat accurate.

(see Shang & Hyndman, 2017). However, it can be approximated by W_h (Wickramasuriya et al., 2018) such that:

$$\mathbb{E} [\hat{e}_{t+h} \hat{e}'_{t+h} | y_1, y_2, \dots, y_t] \quad \text{and} \quad (15)$$

$$\text{VAR} [\tilde{e}_{t+h} | y_1, y_2, \dots, y_t] = SPW_h P' S \quad (16)$$

By minimizing the trace of $SPW_h P' S$ where P is the projection matrix, that is:

$$P = \left(S' \Sigma_h^\dagger S \right)^{-1} S' \Sigma_h^\dagger \hat{y}_n(h)$$

Where $\hat{e}_{t+h} = y_{t+h} - \hat{y}_{t+h}$ and $\tilde{e}_{t+h} = SP\hat{e}_{t+h}$.

6. Results

This section presents the results from CoD modelling of Kenyan female mortality between 1990 and 2016. Based on the varying trends in age-specific mortality as shown in figure (3), we investigate whether there has been a substantial overall change in mortality structure over the years, as outlined by Booth et al. (2002). Since the interest is investigating structural mortality change over time, it suffices to study the mortality index over time. To do this, we investigate the time-varying mortality indices from three models: $k(t)$ from the classical R. D. Lee and Carter (1992) model; adjusted $k(t)$ as described in R. Lee and Miller (2001) and R. D. Lee and Carter (1992); and adjusted $k(t)$ as described by Booth et al. (2001) under Poisson count deaths for the 27 years.

Figure (5a) suggests a fitting period post-2000. On the other hand, a ratio of the mean deviances of base lack of fit and total lack of fit does not show significant mortality change during these years (see figures (5b & 5c)). With limited historical data, it is prudent to utilise as much as possible. Discarding data prior to 2000 would be equivalent to reducing our data by 40%, remaining with only 15 years' data to fit and cross-validate the models. Upon further checks, we elected to use the whole dataset. It is noteworthy that female mortality is insensitive to the adjustment procedure used.

6.1. Models Fitting & Evaluation

We proceeded to fit three models: Renshaw and Haberman's extension of the LC model (Renshaw & Haberman, 2006) where $\beta_x^{(0)} = \beta_x^{(1)} = 1$, which is the most stable (Haberman & Renshaw, 2011); Penalised Splines (PS) and the noble Constrained Penalised Spline (CPS) to both by-cause and the aggregate mortalities from 1990 to 2006. APC model was preferred over LC purely for model comparability reasons¹⁶. To circumvent convergence issues cited by Hunt and Villegas (2015), the APC model's parameter initial values were set to those from the LC model, as suggested by Currie (2016). For CPS model, we set the initial parameters to $\delta_L^a = 0.025$, $\delta_L^t = 0.25$, $\delta_U^a = 0.975$ and $\delta_U^t = 0.75$ following the recommendations by Camarda (2019).

¹⁶APC model has the cohort term.

Table 2: RMSE for total mortality over 10-year horizon.

	APC	CPS	PS
MinT	0.01063	0.00602	0.00861
BU	0.00967	0.00653	0.00842
TD	0.01033	0.00604	0.00419

The models were used to produce 10-year mortality forecasts to test the goodness of fit. These were cross-validated using the observed mortalities between 2007 and 2016. To do this, the forecasts were first reconciled using three approaches: Top-down proportional reconciliation approach (TD), bottom-up proportional reconciliation approach (BU), and optimal combination by trace minimisation (MinT). Root mean squared error (RMSE), mean percentage error (MPE), mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), Theil's U and logarithmic transform of the accuracy ratio ($\log(\text{AR})$) were then calculated to assess the out-of-sample forecasting performance of the models.

Figure 6: RMSE for total mortality over 10-year horizon.

Overall, the CPS model is the most stable of the three models evaluated. The out-of-sample accuracy of the CPS model does not significantly rely on the reconciliation approach used, as shown in table (2) and figure (6). This result implies that restricting the forecasts to past observed mortality using the CPS model reduces the model's sensitivity to the reconciliation method used. Reconciling the forecasts based on the less erratic all-cause mortality also improves the forecasts' accuracy. Additionally, the BU approach produces better out-of-sample forecasts, as seen from figure (6). Finally, the model would benefit from forecast reconciliation if we constrain future mortality based on past experience.

We have also plotted RMSEs for by-cause mortalities as shown in figure (7). Besides TB and HIV/AIDS, the CPS model performs better for all CoD. For cardiovascular, the forecasts produced by fitting an APC model without reconciliation substantially outperform all the other models. Generally, the APC model outperforms the other two models if the mortalities have the typical Nike shape, such as that of cardiovascular, as shown in figure (4b). On the other hand, the

Figure 5: Mortality structural change over time.

Figure 7: By-cause RMSE over 10-year forecasting horizon.

525 PS model is best suited for short-term forecasts. The
 out-of-sample forecast error increases faster for the PS
 model than the other two models.

530 It is also noteworthy that for all CoDs, the CPS model
 is less sensitive to the reconciliation approach chosen
 than the other models and hence the most stable

model. Additionally, the CPS model is more reliable
 irrespective of how noisy the mortality pattern is. Ad-
 ditionally, for noisy mortality series such as that of
 HIV/AIDS, the CPS gives a compromise between the
 more restrictive APC model and the more flexible PS
 model, as shown in figure (7h).

535

(g) TB

(h) HIV/AIDS

(i) Cancer

(j) Others

Figure 7: By-cause RMSE over 10-year forecasting horizon.

6.2. Model Selection

We have developed a scoring methodology to select the best mortality model for Kenyan data. We have scored on a scale of 1 to 5 based on the following:

- 10-year running RMSE & MAPE i.e. ranking figures (7a) to (7j), and similar figures produced using MAPE.
- 10-year running e_0 & e_0^\dagger i.e. we also calculated and cross-validated the mean lifespan (e_0) and lifespan variations (e_0^\dagger)¹⁷. We then produced similar graphs as in figure (7) for both RMSE and MAPE and scored them above.
- 10-year total out-of-sample RMSE, MPE, MAPE, Theil's U & $\log(AR)$ i.e. ranking the out-of-sample performances based on each of these measures for the whole 10-year forecasting period.
- 10-year total e_0 & e_0^\dagger i.e. out-of-sample mean lifespan and lifespan variation measures for the whole ten-year forecasting period.
- Model stability i.e. we defined a model as stable if the out-of-sample performance does not significantly fluctuate across the CoD.

The scores have been summed up and summarised in table (4). In general, the CPS model produces more accurate forecasts. Forecast reconciliation by trace min-

¹⁷This is a measure of the average number of life years lost at birth (see Vaupel & Romo, 2003; Zhang & Vaupel, 2009, for more details).

Figure 8: RMSE for HIV/AIDS mortality over 10-year horizon for APC and PS models; and 5%, 50% and 95% constrain levels on the CPS model.

imisation works best with the CPS model. When applying the APC model, forecasting individual CoD and then summing up the forecasts to produce all-cause forecasts will produce more accurate forecasts.

6.3. Rationale for CPS model

We now investigate the impact the constraints on the CPS model have on its performance. In figure (8), we present RMSE for APC and PS models and compare them with those from CPS models under different constraints. By constraining the fluctuations in the rate of ageing to only 5% of previously observed fluctuations¹⁸, the results approach those obtained from the

¹⁸CPS_5 model in figures (8) & (9).

Figure 9: MAPE for all-cause mortality over 10-year horizon for APC and PS models; and 5%, 50% and 95% constrain levels on the CPS model.

Figure 10: Female all-cause mortality for Kenya between 1990 and 2042.

575 APC model. Effectively, we are restricting the mortality index to be linear, which is generally the assumption in most extensions of the LC model, (R. Lee & Miller, 2001).

580 On the other hand, by allowing 95% of past fluctuations to continue into the future¹⁹, our results approach those from the more flexible PS model. We also show in figure (9) that we can produce similar results as APC and PS models by appropriately setting CPS model constraint parameters. This means we can conveniently incorporate knowledge of past mortality into modelling while retaining both the statistical modelling rigour and plausible demographic features.

590 To check if our forecasts are better than mere guesses, we calculated Theil's U for all-cause and by-cause mortalities for all the models and reconciliation approaches. Results showed that applying a reconciliation approach significantly improves out-of-sample forecasting performance for all models, with the CPS model having the best performance.

595 6.4. Mortality Forecasting

We then fitted the CPS model to all-cause and each COD, forecasted mortality until 2042, and then reconciled the forecasts. Figure (10) shows the rainbow plot of the Kenyan female forecasted mortality. Mortality is expected to continue declining, albeit at a slower rate. This is due to the recent deceleration in mortality improvements as seen in figure (3).

605 We also investigated the projected mortality improvements over the years for selected ages as shown in figure (11). Other than for very young ages (see figure (11a)), a deceleration in mortality improvements has been observed in the recent past, and this trend is projected to continue. We have also applied the residual bootstrap algorithm to construct a confidence interval for these projections. At older ages, the uncertainty around mortality estimates increases (see figures (11a) to (11d)) due to the decline in the amount of available data at these ages.

610 Finally, we used these projections to calculate the pro-

jected mean lifespan²⁰ (figure (12a)) and lifespan variations²¹ (figure (12b)). Our model projects a female life expectancy of 73.3 years [72.4, 74.1] in 2042, compared to the UN's 70.0 years (United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division [UNPD], 2022). It also projects the average number of life years lost at birth to smoothly decline from 15.9 years in 2016 to 13.8 years [13.6, 14.0] in 2042. Kenya's population is, therefore, ageing faster than previously projected, and this finding has significant implications for healthcare financing. An older population will likely increase healthcare demand, so proper planning is essential.

7. Conclusion

630 In figures (8) and (9), we have illustrated the application of the CPS model in mortality modelling. We show that the constraint parameters can be chosen to produce similar results as that from the restrictive models, such as the APC model, or the more flexible ones, like the PS model. It can be used as a sliding scale between these models. We also show that the application of this model produces better forecasts. Using the CPS model to project life expectancy shows an increase in life expectancy by 3.3 years from the UN's projections. In a country with limited resources like Kenya, and when most countries strive to achieve UHC²², this finding has significant implications for healthcare budgeting.

635 This paper proposes applying the novel CPS model and the trace minimisation reconciliation approach (MinT) to model mortality with irregular patterns. The CPS model allows us to utilise all mortality information, except it constrains future mortality to observed age profiles and time trends. The trace minimisation reconciliation ensures that we produce coherent forecasts. We have applied these methods to Kenyan mortality data from 1990 to 2016 and used them to project mortality until 2042. The out-of-sample results show that the CPS model is stable and is not very sensitive to the reconciliation approach used. We have also shown

²⁰ e_0 .

²¹ e_0^{\dagger} .

²²Universal health coverage.

¹⁹CPS_95 model in figures (8) & (9).

Figure 11: Female mortality forecasts at selected ages and their confidence interval.

Figure 12: Mean lifespan (e_0) and lifespan variation (e_0^\dagger) forecasts and their confidence intervals.

655 that the MinT reconciliation approach produces better
reconciled forecasts when applied with the CPS model.

Moreover, we have illustrated how we can incorpo-
rate prior knowledge in the forecasts without throwing
away mortality data. By applying constraints on the
660 rates of ageing and mortality change over the years,
we can constrain future mortality to observed age and
time trends. Therefore, prior knowledge, e.g. on near-
future breakthroughs in medicine, could easily be incor-
porated into the forecasting using this method. It
665 can also be used as a "what if" tool, given that it can
be used as a sliding scale between the more restrictive
and flexible mortality models.

A possible area of further research is the application
of the CPS model within the functional mortality data

analysis (see for example Shang & Hyndman, 2017, 670
and the references therein). There is also growing
research on model averaging techniques in mortality
modelling. For example, Shang and Booth (2020) have
applied model averaging to fertility forecasting, showing
675 improvement in the forecasts. It would be interest-
ing to see how altering the constraint levels and apply-
ing model average techniques would impact the overall
model performance of the CPS model.

Appendices

A. Mathematical formulation

A.1. Relationship between Central Death Rate and Force of Mortality

The central death rate, $m(x, t)$, is defined as

$$m(x, t) = \frac{D(x, t)}{E^c(x, t)} \quad (17)$$

$$= \frac{D(x, t)}{\int_0^1 l_{x+s, t+s} ds} \quad (18)$$

$$= \frac{q_{x, t}}{\int_0^1 p_{x+s, t+s} ds} \quad (19)$$

$$= \frac{\int_0^1 e^{-\int_0^s \mu_{x+k, t+k} dk} \mu_{x+s, t+s} ds}{\int_0^1 e^{-\int_0^s \mu_{x+k, t+k} dk} ds} \quad (20)$$

$$= \mu_{x, t} \quad (21)$$

where all the notations carry their usual meanings and noting that

$$\mu_x = -\frac{1}{l_x} \frac{dl_x}{dx} \quad (22)$$

by definition. The implicit assumption here is that of constant force of mortality, as defined elsewhere. It is also referred to as the central mortality rate.

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Table 3: International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10) codes mapped to the causes of death used in this paper.

Cause	ICD-10 Codes
LRI	A48.1, A70, B97.4-B97.6, J09-J15.8, J16-J16.9, J20-J21.9, P23.0-P23.4, U04-U04.9
Malaria	B50-B53.8
Cancer	C00-C97, D00.1, D00.2, D01.0-D01.3, D02.0-D02.3, D03-D07.2, D07.4-D07.5, D09.0, D09.2-D09.3, D09.8, D10.0-D10.7, D11-D13.7, D14.0-D14.3, D15-D16.9, D22-D24.9, D26.0-D28.1, D28.7, D29.0-D29.8, D30.0-D30.8, D31-D31.9, D34-D35.2, D35.5-D36.7, D37.1-D37.5, D38.0-D38.5, D39.1-D39.2, D39.8, D40.0-D40.8, D41.0-D41.8, D44.0-D44.8, D48.0-D48.6, D49.2-D49.4
HIV/AIDS	B20-B24.9
Deficiency	D50.1-D50.8, D51-D52.0, D52.8-D53.9, E00-E02, E40-E46.9, E51-E61.9, E63-E64.0, E64.2-E64.9, M12.1
TB	A15-A19.9, B90-B90.9, K67.3, K93.0, M49.0, N74.1, P37.0, U84.3
Cardiovascular	B33.2, G45-G46.8, I01-I01.9, I02.0, I05-I09.9, I11-I11.9, I20-I25.9, I28-I28.8, I30-I31.1, I31.8-I37.8, I38-I41.9, I42.1-I42.8, I43-I43.9, I47-I48.9, I51.0-I51.4, I60-I63.9, I65-I66.9, I67.0-I67.3, I67.5-I67.6, I68.0-I68.2, I69.0-I69.3, I70.2-I70.8, I71-I73.9, I77-I83.9, I86-I89.0, I89.9, I98, K75.1
Injuries	V00-V86.9, V87.2-V87.3, V88.2-V88.3, V90-V98.8
Meningitis	A39-A39.9, A87-A87.9, G00.0-G00.8, G03-G03.8
Others	Everything else not included above

Table 4: Summary of Model selection for COD mortality modelling.

Cause	Approach	Female			Male		
		APC	CPS	PS	APC	CPS	PS
Summary by Reconciliation Approach							
Overall	MinT	105	211	122	108	205	123
	BU	172	141	113	181	144	119
	TD	139	153	121	163	157	116
Summary by Mortality Data Used							
All-cause	All	51	110	113	53	116	91
COD	All	365	395	243	399	390	267
Summary by Reconciliation Approach and Mortality Data Used							
All-cause	MinT	15	41	35	17	43	24
	BU	20	32	37	19	32	39
	TD	16	37	41	17	41	28
COD	MinT	90	170	87	91	162	99
	BU	154	108	76	165	111	79
	TD	125	115	80	149	113	87
OVERALL							
		416	505	356	452	506	358